

Physical Education and Sports Administration in India

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Abstract:

Constitutionally, sports like education is a national obligation under the Directive Principles of State Policy and is listed as a State subject which means that the promotion of sports as a measure of human welfare and health is the sole responsibility of the State Government. The Union Government may, as and when necessary and expedient, formulate policies and issue directives to invigorate the effort of the State Governments. It is interesting that sports, the essence of physical education was usually tagged with education, Its emergence as a distinct subject is a recent development. There are two main bases for this. One, from sports angle, education is a closed system. In educational institutions - schools, colleges, universities - sports is regarded as an adjunct of education. The primary objective of a student's life is "study" and not competitive sport. With regard to promotion of sports, the responsibility of the education sector is limited i.e. beyond certain period of time, it ceases to look after the athlete (the moment he passes out of the school/university). Being well-established, the education sector offers better prospects of disciplined growth of sports, it has, at times, produced the finest young sports persons. Its limitations are obvious. For instance, it caters only to student population, common man is beyond its purview. Second, sport is a bio-social phenomenon - an outgrowth of the instinct of pugnacity, gregariousness, etc. The social interaction through sports is possible more with club-system than through education channel. The non-education sector (sports-association hierarchy) is the de facto godfather of sports and is well-established but because it comprises voluntary associations, it is plagued by numerous financial and organizational ailments. The government has no control over it. In the evolution of competitive sport as a global phenomenon, the non-education sector (sport associations) has played an important role.

Keywords: *Administration, Physical education, Sports, and India.*

Introduction:

For the last four decades, an attempt has been made to declare physical education a required curricular subject by reducing academic load but this has not been possible due to such factors as (1) want of firm sport policy (2) lack of will and determination on the part of the government (3) absence of professional commitment, (4) apathy of the academic, and (5) lack of appropriate sport infrastructure in the educational institutions. The Education Sector is a fertile ground for excellence in sports but utterly poor in resources. The governmental budgetary

support for sports in education sector is not even a drop in the ocean. Even the bare minimum pupil-teacher ratio of 250:1 at school, as recommended in the National Plan of Physical Education and Recreation (1956) has been impossible to maintain. Rather with the unprecedented influx of students in schools, this ratio has tilted for the worse. Physical education and sport at schools exist only in name. The sport scenario in colleges and universities has worsened over the decades basically for two reasons: (1) The Indian society has become more competitive today and there is a rat race for more lucrative jobs and attractive

careers which leaves hardly any time for sport, and (2) in comparison to active sport, other passive means of recreation attract the youth more. Moreover, with tremendous increase in incentives, awards, rewards, privileges, benefits etc. most student athletes have begun to use sports achievement as a spring board for entering highly priced careers and courses than pursue sport for excellence. The organizational set-up of Sports Administration in Indian Education Sector is discussed hereunder with actual (not hypothetical) on-going practices.

Association of Indian Universities:

With a view "to promoting university activities, especially by way of sharing information and increasing cooperation in the field of education, culture, sports and allied areas", the Inter-Varsity Board (IVB) was founded in March, 1925 as a result of the deliberations of the Conference of the Vice-Chancellors of the Universities by the then Viceroy of India at Shimla, in 1924. In 1973, the IVB was transformed into an autonomous registered Society and christened as the Association of Indian Universities with unconventional Agriculture Universities, Medical Institutes, Women's Universities, Institutions of National Importance etc. also becoming its members. Today, its membership is roughly 220. In order to encourage sports in the Indian Universities, an independent Inter-University Sports Board was formed in 1941 which after the reorganization of IUB in 1973, became a division of the AIU.

The AIU (sports division) is chiefly responsible for 1. assisting the development of sports and games in the universities, 2. preparing the annual sports calendar for inter-university tournaments (Zonal and All India) for men and women (sections) and ensuring their smooth conduct, 3. organizing coaching camps for the

university and college students, 4. raising and training the combined universities' teams and arranging their participation in the national tournaments of selected games/sports (for this purpose the AIU is a member of about twelve National Sports Federations), 5. selecting and training the Indian Universities' teams to participate in the World Universiad and other international fixtures, and making possible the exchange visit of teams from abroad, 6. liaising with Department of Youth Affairs and Sports, Netaji Subhas National Institute of Sports, Sports Authority of India, Lakshmbai National Institute of Sports, etc. for financial support, technical professional assistance for the upliftment of standard of sports and games in the universities, 7. extending financial assistance to universities which opt to organize inter-varsity tournaments, 8. getting trophies and awards (Maulana Abdul Kalam Azad Trophy and Cash awards, Dr. B.L.Gupta Inter-University General Championship trophy) bestowed upon the winning universities annually, 9. projecting the Indian University teams to participate in the World University Games and the World University Championships subject to the approval of the Department of Youth Affairs and Sports, and finally, 10. helping the university physical education departments to conduct workshops, seminars, national conferences etc. on sports occasionally.

The sports division of the AIU is headed by a Deputy Secretary who is assisted by a few junior level officials in the discharge of his duties. The AIU (Sports Division) does not brook interference in the internal affairs of the university departments of physical education such as organizing intercollegiate tournaments. It formulates its policies and programmes through the Sports Committee of directors of physical education of universities (in rotation) headed by a Vice-Chancellor. Due to several fissures and

faults in its policies, powers, programmes, organizational and administrative set-up, the AIU has yet to prove its effectiveness as a strong sports administration.

University Department of Physical Education:

As the highest seat of learning, a university is an autonomous statutory complex structure of faculties, teaching and non-teaching departments, research divisions, administrative offices and welfare units. Irrespective of their status affiliating, residential or institutional- all universities have a Department of Physical Education usually headed by a Director with an appropriate administrative set up.

There are three types of physical education departments exists in the universities of India: (1) Non-teaching Department where the functions, duties and responsibilities involve training, coaching, conduct of intercollegiate and/or inter-university tournaments, and sponsoring university teams for inter-university competitions; (2) Teaching Department catering to academics of physical education and (3) Composite Department involving both administrative and academic responsibilities.

College Physical Education Department:

Except where physical education is a teaching subject, the college physical education department is a non-teaching department headed by the senior most lecturer generally known to the students as DPE (Director of Physical Education). The number of physical education teachers in a college depends upon student-strength. The major functions of the Physical Education Department in a college are 1. To organize intramural sports competitions, 2. To prepare college teams to participate in inter-collegiate competitions, 3. To host inter-collegiate competition(s) allotted to the college by university physical education department, 4. To conduct instruction classes if

and when obligatory, 5. To prepare budget for the department and operate it after it is duly approved, 6. To get sport infrastructure constructed and be responsible for its care and maintenance, 7. To procure sports equipment, maintain its record and ensure its up-keep, 8. To record sports achievements of the college and athletes, and prepare annual report there of, 9. To take care of athletic honour boards, trophies and cups won by the institution, 10. To look after sports hostel(s) if established in the college, 11. To organize annual recreation fetes and sports festivals, 12. To provide health service and health supervision to the students and maintain their physico-medical record.

An appropriate organizational set-up for a college department of physical education must be based on ground realities rather than Utopian ideals. No college can afford to have too many physical education teachers but there ought to be a fairly good number of supporting staff whose services are utilized for running activity routines, organizing tournaments and ensuring care and maintenance of the sport infrastructure and equipment. This apart, the cooperation of other faculty members may be sought while organizing athletic meets, tournaments etc.

School Games Federation of India:

Like any other Sports Association, the SGFI is an elected body of the nominated representatives of the State Education Departments (generally state sports organizers/directors). Being an apex body the SGFI looks after the competitive sports in the school sector. On the one hand, it is affiliated with the Indian Olympic Association and on the other with the World school sports body. It conducts the National School Games regularly and is responsible for talent-scouting, training of promising school athletes and sponsoring them for the international fixtures under the patronage

of the Indian Olympic Association. The financial support for the SGFI comes from state education departments, the union government and the Indian Olympic Association. The SGFI has nothing to do directly with routine physical education instruction, health, fitness programmes for all etc. in schools.

State Education Sports Wing:

The set-up of the State Education Sport Wing differs from state to state. In most states, the Education Sport Wing is headed by an additional director/joint director or a deputy director with reasonably staffed administrative office. In general, the head of the Sport Wing works under the Director of Public Instruction but in some cases, he may receive directions direct from the education secretariat. No clear-cut policies are followed in structuring a state education sport wing. The wing subsists on the state funding, grants from the central authority/government and part of the sports fee realized from schools. The major functions of the State Education Sports Wing are: (1) to nurture state sports schools, school sports wings, and sports hostels, thereby concentrating on training of promising athletes, (2) to conduct state sports meets and competitions, and (3) to select and prepare state teams for participation in national fixtures. Sometime the control and supervision of physical education teachers is vested in the sports wing. The sports wing also employs and deploys coaches and supporting staff.

The assistant district education officers (PE) are part of the District Education Administration. Their duties are mainly supervisory and advisory with no financial powers. On the one hand, they look after sports wings and hostels on the directions from the state sports wing, on the other hand they organize the district sports tournaments for the school students and prepare district teams with the help of

physical education teachers and cooperation of the heads of the institution. Except during district tournaments, sports days, mass activity demonstrations etc. the Assistant Education Officer, Physical Education have no supervisory control over physical education teachers in private schools. The district (education) sports administration receives a portion of the sports fees realized from the students, and also budgetary support from the State Education department mainly for organizing sports tournaments.

In schools, there is one or more physical education teachers who take instructional classes, prepare school teams for participation in inter-scholastic tournaments, look after sports infrastructure, and procure sports equipment within budgetary provisions. They also organize play days, sports festivals and intramurals. Where physical education is a compulsory subject, the working schedule of physical educators is very tight otherwise they are given other managerial duties. In schools, physical education is a neglected subject chiefly for two reasons. (1) heads of the institution (and academics) have scant respect for sports activities, and (2) physical education and sports is no priority subject. The physical education scenario in schools is utterly dismal and needs revolutionary changes with regard to its organizational and functional aspects.

Conclusion:

Education Sector covers educational institutions where physical education and sports - once considered simply extra-curricular activities are a part and parcel of general educational process. In some States, physical education and sports is a regular academic, curricular activity, in others it is an after-school programme and in yet others it is neither. The Education Sector undoubtedly is the cradle of institutionalized sport

but it does require complete renovation, rejuvenation and revamping.

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